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THE GEOPOLITICS OF SEA POWER: THE ROLE OF THE ROYAL NAVY AND THE IMPERIAL RUSSIAN NAVY WITHIN THE GREATER MEDITERRANEAN 1546-1870

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Аннотация. В статье представлен исторический обзор геополитической роли Королевского флота и Императорского Российского флота в международных отношениях в регионе Большого Средиземноморья в период с 1546 по 1870 годы.

Abstract. The article provides an historical overview of the geopolitical role of the Royal Navy and the Imperial Russian Navy in the international relations of the Greater Mediterranean between 1546-1870.

Ключевые слова: геополитика, морская мощь, Большое Средиземноморье, Турецкие проливы, Чёрное море.

Keywords: Geopolitical, Seapower, Greater Mediterranean, Turkish Straits, Black Sea.

Geopolitics is a body of international relations theory which argues that geography can powerfully influence, but not determine, national policy (LeDonne, 1997, p. xiv). Since maritime policy is at all times an instrument of national policy, the role of sea power must therefore always be considered within the framework of the nation's geopolitically shaped grand strategy (Gray, 1990; Tangredi, 2001; Ortmann and Whittaker, 2016). So within the framework of their respective grand strategies of Britain and Russia, this paper will first look at the role of the Royal Navy in the Greater Mediterranean between 1546-1815 and then examine the interacting role of the Imperial Russian Navy and the Royal Navy in the Greater Mediterranean between 1796-1870.

The Royal Navy and the Greater Mediterranean 1546-1815

In developing an offensive 'Blue Water' ocean-going naval capability to advance its imperial expansion into the wider world, from the 16th century England was careful to adopt a defensive strategy in dealing with its imperial rivals in European waters - Portugal, Spain, France, and the Dutch Republic (Baugh, 1988). As an island power on the periphery of Europe, England was in the fortunate position where it could utilize its sea power to pursue a grand strategy of 'Off-shore Balancing' (Mearsheimer, 2014, pp. 261-266). To contain any state seeking hegemony (dominance), and maintain a balance of power in Europe, England could use its naval forces either directly - to deliver military forces into Europe and enforce long term naval blockades, or indirectly to underpin coercive naval diplomacy (Till, 2018, Chapter 13). Where necessary, the services of

mercenaries could be purchased, and tangible incentives could be provided to allies to adhere to anti-hegemonic coalitions (Gray, 1990, p. 118). Hence, prior to 1914 Britain never sent a major portion of her own army to fight on the continent of Europe (the 'Continental Commitment'), and even the armies of Marlborough and Wellington, Britain's two most renowned generals, were primarily composed of European, rather than British, troops (Layne, 1970, p. 310; Rodger, 1992). As a strategy of limited commitment, utilizing the armies or mercenaries of continental neighbours to further its own national interests, Britain's strategy of off-shore balancing was unsurprisingly viewed by many of its continental neighbours as a 'strategy of irrelevance', amounting to what Napoleon termed 'pygmy combinations' (Mackesy, 1957, p. 91). So within Britain's grand strategy, what geopolitical role did the Royal Navy play in the Greater Mediterranean in the centuries before 1815?

Historically, Britain's naval forces had comprised the 'King's Great Ships' (largely merchant ships), mobilized for service in an *ad hoc* fashion and then dispersed after service – a relatively simple and economical arrangement. However, in the last years of the reign of Henry VIII in 1546, a Royal Navy was finally established as a Department of State with its own dockyards and purpose-built warships. Although in 1588 this nascent English navy of Elizabeth I rebuffed the efforts of a Spanish 'Great Armada' to effect an invasion of England, it was not until 1650 that the key Royal Navy Western Squadron (later retitled the Channel Fleet, the Home Fleet, and finally the Grand Fleet) was established in Plymouth. In the (correct) calculations of the Admiralty, the maintenance of a powerful Western Squadron in the 'Narrow Seas' of the Western Approaches of the English Channel, would enable England to both deter invasions fleets and interdict the despatch of hostile European naval forces into the wider world (Duffy, 1992; Rodger, 1998; Rodger, 2006b; Kennedy, 2017, pp. 100-101). Four years later, to exert more influence in the great seaway of the Greater Mediterranean which flanked the southern perimeter of Europe, stretching 2,000 miles from Gibraltar to the Dardanelles, in 1654 a Royal Navy Mediterranean Squadron of around 30 ships was established (Grainger, 2017, p. 34). But it was not until the War of the Spanish Succession (1701-1713) that an Anglo-Portuguese Treaty of 1703 agreed that Lisbon, located 350 miles from the Straits of Gibraltar, should be a forward wintering base for the Mediterranean Squadron (Kennedy, 2017, p. 88). By the conclusion of the war, England was a significant presence in the western Mediterranean, while a declining Spanish Empire was now effectively a client state of France (Hattendorf, 1995, p. 90). And having seized Gibraltar in 1704, by the 1713 Treaty of Utrecht Britain secured possession *in perpetuity* of what would be, despite its shortcomings, a vital toe-hold in the Mediterranean Sea (Black, 2005, p. 61; Kennedy, 2017, pp. 85-86; Grainger, 2017, pp. 75, 80-81). At this point, the France of Louis XIV was still a formidable state in Western Europe, with a population three times the size and an economy double the size of Britain. Yet over the following hundred years between 1713-1815, Britain successfully fought five separate wars with France (lasting a total of 38 years), and emerged in 1815 as the world's pre-eminent imperial and naval power. Since four of the five wars were largely concerned with colonial rivalries, it is the twenty two years of coalition wars waged between 1793-1815 to deny France hegemony in Europe, in which control of the Greater Mediterranean was of important concern to most of the belligerents, which must be examined.

The War of the First Coalition 1793-1797

Despite the formation in 1793 of the First Coalition of Britain, Austria, Prussia, Holland and Spain to contain Revolutionary France, having failed to take the French

naval base of Toulon, by 1796 the Royal Navy had effectively withdrawn from the Mediterranean (Hattendorf, 1995, pp. 108-9). In these circumstances the French government (the Directory) was happy to authorize Napoleon's audacious proposal to take an expeditionary force of 31,000 men, 170 guns and 1,200 horses to Egypt, establish a French empire in the Eastern Mediterranean, and prepare the way for an eventual French challenge to Britain's position in India (Ingram, 1998, p. 16). Caught unprepared by Napoleon's departure from Toulon, it was not until 1 August 1798 that Nelson's detached squadron tracked down the French expeditionary force to Aboukir Bay at the mouth of the Nile, 20 miles northeast of the port of Alexandria, and annihilated the French fleet (Grainger, 2017, p.151). The 'Battle of the Nile' has been exaggeratedly termed 'the greatest victory in the history of naval warfare' and Nelson has become Britain's 'God of War' (Wilson, 2014, p. 86). However, this decisive exercise of British sea power was followed by a British military defeat of French forces at Alexandria, which underlined the determination within Whitehall that France should never be permitted to project its power east to the Levant and Black Sea and thereby threaten Britain's 'short route to India' - its sea lines of communication through the Greater Mediterranean and then across the isthmus to the Red Sea or down the Tigris or Euphrates Rivers to the Persian Gulf and the Indian Ocean (Baugh, 1988, p. 38; Black 2009, p. 106).

The War of the Second Coalition 1798-1802

A Second Coalition War against France and Spain was initiated by Britain, Austria, Russia, the Ottoman Empire, plus Portugal and Naples. Unfortunately, thanks to the erratic direction of policy by Tsar Paul I, Russia failed to secure Malta as a naval base in the Mediterranean, and the withdrawal of its army from Italy and its warships from the Mediterranean, followed by Napoleon's defeat of Austrian forces at Marengo in June 1800, left Britain without a major European ally (Fuller, 1992, p. 181). As a consequence, in 1802 Britain now signed the Peace of Amiens with France and Spain and promised to withdraw from the island of Malta which it had occupied in 1800 (Longworth, 2005, p. 190). Although the subsequent refusal of Britain to return Malta to French control precipitated a renewal of the war, having none of the drawbacks of Gibraltar for the next 178 years the magnificent Valetta Harbour of Malta would serve as a superior fleet base for the Royal Navy's Mediterranean Squadron (Bartlett, 1963 p. 59; Holland, 2012, pp. 12-15).

The War of the Third Coalition 1804-1807

The formation of a Third Coalition of Britain, Austria, Prussia and Russia saw Nelson's spectacular defeat of a Franco-Spanish fleet at the Battle of Trafalgar on 21 October 1805, at the moment of victory killed on the quarterdeck of his flagship the *Victory*. Critics of the claims made for the leverage of sea power and offshore-balancing have questioned the significance of Trafalgar. One day before Trafalgar, Napoleon's *Grande Armee* defeated Austrian forces at Ulm, and subsequently crushed Austrian and Russian forces at Austerlitz in December 1805, Prussian forces at Jena-Auerstadt in October 1806, and Russian forces at Eylau in February and Friedland in June 1807. It is consequently argued that it was these land-power victories of the *Grande Armee* which ensured that the war of the Third Coalition ended with France in a stronger position in Europe than at the start (Black, 2009, p. 105; Mearsheimer, 2014, pp. 272-79). Conceding that a seapower can never be decisive against a continental power or coalition, naval historians have argued that Trafalgar denied France control of the Mediterranean, and provided the framework for the self-destruction of Napoleon's landlocked empire (Gray, 1989, pp. 4, 23; Gray, 1992, pp. 67, 170; Rodger, 2006a, pp. 84-87; Grainger, 2017, pp. 159-62). As Dominic Lieven has emphasised, 'the most basic

fact about the Napoleonic Wars was that British seapower locked French imperialism into Europe' (Lieven, 2010, p. 16). Denial of the seaway of the Mediterranean to Napoleon came at a heavy price. Apart from the cost of the maintenance of the garrisons at Gibraltar and Malta, by 1808 the Mediterranean Fleet of the Royal Navy comprised eighty vessels, a third of which were 'ships of the line' manned by 28,000 seamen, a force equivalent to a Mediterranean army (Mackesy, 1957, pp. 16-17).

1807-1815

With the publication of Napoleon's Berlin decrees in November 1806, designed to starve Britain of her European trade, it appeared that the Ottoman Empire might join with France. Vice-Admiral Duckworth was therefore sent with six Royal Navy ships of the line to Constantinople to put pressure on Turkey to pull back. Although Duckworth got past the batteries at the Dardanelles and entered the Sea of Marmora, his diplomatic mission achieved nothing, and after his departure Russian Admiral Senyavin blockaded the Dardanelles and in July 1807 won a clear victory over the Turkish fleet (Rodger, 2004, pp. 550-51; Grainger, 2017, pp. 161-62). Meanwhile, as a consequence of the agreements reached by Tsar Alexander I and Napoleon at Tilsit in July 1807, which required that Russia abandon the Mediterranean and adhere to Napoleon's 'Continental System', Anglo-Russian rivalry was born and between November 1807 and July 1812 an odd formal state of war existed between Britain and Russia (Anderson, 1967; Ingram, 1999, p. 281; Orlov, 2015). However, confronted by Russia's efforts to evade his 'Continental System', and concerned to deny London the possibility of an alliance with Russia, ignoring the warnings of some of his senior military and diplomatic advisers, in June 1812 a half-million strong invasion force was led by Napoleon across the Niemen River into Russia (Fuller, 1992, pp. 184-86; Ingram, 1998, pp. 27, 40; Lieven, 2010, pp. 47-52). Having reached Moscow, in the absence of a diplomatic settlement the *Grande Armee* reluctantly commenced a painful withdrawal from Russia. Meanwhile, thanks to Napoleon's desperate measures to implement his 'Continental System', by 1808 the people of the Iberian Peninsula (Spain and Portugal) had risen in revolt against Napoleonic rule. The despatch to the peninsula of a limited British force under Sir Arthur Wellesley (Wellington) in support of this struggle, underlined the value of British sea power, and in June 1813 the victory of Wellington's forces at Vittoria finally destroyed Napoleon's power in the Peninsula (French, 1990, pp.111-118; Gray, 1992, p. 87). Re-entering the war against France, in October 1813 Prussian and Austrian forces, together with Russian forces, now engaged Napoleon's *Grande Armee* in the monumental 'Battle of the Nations' at Leipzig (the largest land battle for a century until World War I), and having sustained casualties of 200,000, the *Grande Armee* was then pursued across Europe, Russian, Prussian and Austrian troops entering Paris in March 1814. With the final victory of British and Prussian forces at Waterloo in June 1815, a combination of land and sea power had contained the bid by France to secure hegemony in Europe (Howard, 1976, pp. 91-2; Strachan, 1983, p. 52; Lieven, 2015, pp. 1-111).

The Imperial Russian Navy and Royal Navy in the Greater Mediterranean 1696- 1870

The Grand Duchy of Muscovy 1480-1613

After enduring more than two centuries of occupation by the Mongol Empire, from 1480 the Grand Duchy of Muscovy looked to compensate for its geostrategic vulnerability by territorial expansion. To pre-empt external attacks, in the 1550s Tsar Ivan IV (1533-1584) moved east and annexed the Tatar Khanates of Kazan and Astrakhan, thereby gaining control of the whole course of the Volga River. However, unable to force an outlet to the Baltic Sea during the Livonian War with the Swedes and

Poles (1558-82), Muscovy remained reliant on its single White Sea port of Arkhangelsk, ice-bound for half the year, while thanks to the vulnerability of its southern and western borders, in 1571 Crimean Tatars besieged and burnt some of Moscow, and during the Time of Troubles Polish forces briefly occupied Moscow (1610-1612) (Berryman, 2019, p. 288).

The Russian Empire 1613-1762

Following the election by the *Zemskii sobor* of Mikhail Romanov as Tsar in 1613, although Russian adventurers pushed across Siberia to reach the Pacific Ocean, it was not until Turkish forces failed to take Vienna in 1683 that Tsar Peter the Great chose to seek an outlet to the oceans of the world through the Black Sea. In 1696, after an initial failed attempt, the Ottoman fortress of Azov was seized, Taganrog was identified as a naval base for an Azov fleet, and an Imperial Russian Navy was founded (150 years after the Royal Navy) (Fuller, 1992, p. 38). However, without control of Kerch, which controlled the exit from the Sea of Azov to the Black Sea, Azov and Taganrog were worthless, and following another Russo-Turkish war, by the 1711 Treaty of Pruth the fortress at Taganrog was dismantled and the Azov fleet was destroyed (LeDonne, 1997, p. 23; Longworth, 2005, pp.157-58). Meanwhile, with the onset of a Great Northern War with Sweden (1700-1721), the focus of Peter the Great's attention shifted to the Baltic Sea, and in 1703 he founded a great new capital city of St Petersburg and established a Baltic Fleet at Kronstadt. Russia's modest Baltic Fleet was built to support the coercion of Sweden and Denmark by Russia's ground forces, not to engage an offensive Royal Navy if it entered the Baltic. That role was left to the fortresses, mines and flotillas of Kronstadt on Kotlin Island, the most heavily defended naval base in the world (Lambert, 2023, pp. 35-7). It is argued that these initiatives were not vanity projects but reflected Peter the Great's good understanding of the mutual relationship of land power and sea power and the efficacy of combined land and sea operations (Fuller, 1992, p. 69).

1762-1815

After thirty seven years of drift which followed the death of Peter the Great in 1725, it was only following the accession to power of Catherine II in 1762 that Russian forces were despatched down to the Black Sea and from 1768 engaged in a six year war with the Ottoman Empire (1768-1774). At the start of the war, Catherine despatched two squadrons from the Baltic to the Mediterranean, and in support of the Orlov Revolt of 1770 (a Greek insurrection against Ottoman rule and a precursor of the later Greek War of Independence) most of the Ottoman Navy was destroyed by the Russian squadrons in the famous Battle of Chesma Bay in the Aegean Sea off Chios. At this point Russia became a naval power in the Greater Mediterranean (Mitchell, 1974, pp. 57-66; Gorshkov, 1979, p. 75; Black, 2005, p. 84). By the 1774 Treaty of Kutchuk-Kainardji, Russia re-secured the ports of Azov and Taganrog, plus the fortresses of Kerch and Kinburn at the mouth of the Dnieper River, established a protectorate over Crimea, and for the first time in two centuries secured the right to send her merchant ships through the Turkish Straits and keep warships in the Black Sea. Nine years later, in 1783 Russia annexed the Crimean Peninsula and established a Russian Black Sea Fleet with its base of Sevastopol,- a transfer of international responsibility that was recognized by Turkey with its signing of the 1792 Treaty of Jassy (Gorshkov, 1979, p. 76; Longworth, 2005, p. 178; Melvin, 2017, p. 60). At this juncture the Imperial Russian Navy, the fourth naval power in the world, deployed 51 ships of the line in the Baltic Sea and 7 in the Black Sea (Black, 2005 p. 91; Grainger 2017, pp. 141-42). Reflecting the dominance of territorial concerns and powerful land forces in the grand strategy of Imperial Russia, from its inception the regional tasks of the Black Sea Fleet were to match the Turkish Navy,

provide wartime defence for Russia's new south-western flank, including the new Black Sea ports, and serve as a 'second arm' to provide logistic and amphibious support for the Russian army in its efforts to deal with Muslim guerrillas down the Circassian coast of the Black Sea. The long term geostrategic goal of Russia's Black Sea policy was to secure an ability to close the Black Sea to the fleets of Russia's enemies while providing unimpeded access for her warships to the Greater Mediterranean (Berryman, 2017, pp. 58-59).

1815-1853

Quite apart from the assistance Russia had given to the Greek independence struggle in the Battle of Chesma 1770, and its major contribution to the coalition containment of Napoleonic France, following the slaughter of Greeks by Turkish forces, in 1827 Russian responded to calls for international humanitarian intervention and despatched a squadron from the Baltic Fleet to the Mediterranean to participate with British and French naval forces in the annihilation of the Turkish-Egyptian fleet in the Battle of Navarino Bay, a key event in the struggle for Greek independence (Black, 2005, p. 121). Nonetheless, following another brief Russo-Turkish War of 1828 and the gains Russia secured around the Black Sea by the 1829 Treaty of Adrianople, Whitehall was concerned that, having eliminated French designs for hegemony in Europe, Russia's growing influence in the Black Sea might pose a threat to the security of the British Empire's sea and land lines of communication to India (Clayton, 1971, Part II; Jelavich, 1973, p. 14; Ingram, 1999, pp. 270-721). And in what was in effect the first 'Cold War', suspicions in Britain moved from watchfulness in the 1820's to open hostility by the early 1850s (Longworth, 2005, p. 205; Berryman, 2019, p. 290). Paradoxically, by the 1820s Russia's Foreign Minister, Karl Nesselrode, had concluded that for the moment Russia's wisest strategy was to maintain a weak Ottoman Empire which could be persuaded not to side with Russia's enemies, and to work with the Great Powers to maintain the international regime for the Turkish Straits established by the Anglo-Turkish Treaty of 1809, which specified that no non-Turkish warships could pass the Straits while Turkey was at peace (Fuller, 1992, p. 222; Berryman, 2017, p. 59). However, following Russia's intervention against an Egyptian challenge to the Ottoman Empire, although the 1833 Treaty of Unkiar Skelessi seemed to uphold the 1809 rules, aspects of the treaty seemed to imply that should Russia feel threatened by Britain or France, while the Dardanelles would be closed to their warships, the Bosphorus, on which Constantinople stood, would be open to Russian warships and thereby Russian influence. In response to these suspicions, citing the 'ancient rule of the Sultans' who had closed the Straits in 1475, Britain pushed through the establishment of an international 1841 London Straits Convention, which re-stated the 1809 requirements that while Turkey was at peace, Russian warships, like all other foreign warships, would be banned from the Bosphorus as well as the Dardanelles (Clayton, 1971, pp. 71-2; Jelavich, 1973, pp. 17-19; Hosking, 2012, pp. 279-80; Paine, 2013, p. 548). Since no foreign-built warships could be imported by Russia into the Black Sea while Turkey was at peace, warships for the Russian Black Sea Fleet would have to be built in Black Sea ports. In effect the Black Sea Fleet of the Imperial Russian Navy was 'bottled up' in the Black Sea. Moreover, the authorities in St Petersburg were aware that should Russia find herself at war with the Ottoman Empire, British, French, and other non-Turkish warships would then be free to enter the Black Sea to attack Russia (Clayton, 1971, pp. 84-5). It was precisely this circumstance which materialized in 1853.

The Crimean War and After 1853-1870

The build up to the so-called Crimean War may be briefly traced. The focus will be on the role of British and Russian seapower. Thanks to mounting disagreements between Russia and the Ottoman Empire in 1853 over the Holy Places in Jerusalem, Russia's despatch of forces into the Danube Principalities to back up its 'coercive diplomacy' triggered a Turkish declaration of war on Russia in October 1853, following which in November a Turkish squadron at Sinope was annihilated by Russia's Black Sea Fleet. With the rejection of Anglo-French demands that Russia withdraw its forces from the Principalities, in March 1854 Britain and France declared war on Russia and 20,000 British and 40,000 French troops were escorted through the Turkish Straits to the Turkish port of Varna. But with the threat of possible Austrian military intervention, in the summer of 1854 Russia withdrew its army from the Principalities. Confronted by this unexpected pull-back, in London the Cabinet nonetheless agreed to pursue the strategy of a 'preventive war' to cut back and weaken the Russian Empire. As the Russophobe Palmerston later admitted in 1855, 'The main and real object of the war was to curb the aggressive ambition of Russia' (Figs, 2010, p. 195). The transfer of allied troops to the Crimean Peninsula in September 1854 was easily effected since with inferior naval forces Russia avoided fleet action and relied on its coast defences, cannon and minefields (Lambeth 2023, p. 40). However, Anglo-French seapower proved capable of sustaining expeditionary forces in the Crimea with greater logistic ease than the Russian Empire (lacking adequate rail and road communications) could reinforce its army, and after heavy fighting in a year-long siege, in September 1855 the great naval base of Sevastopol was taken. In the spring of 1856, two considerations pushed Russia into peace negotiations. First, the possible entry into the war of Austria, Prussia and Sweden. And second, an awareness that preparations were in hand for the Royal Navy to despatch a coastal fleet of more than 200 ships into the Baltic (including 18 steam warships, 100 gunboats, 46 monitors and 2 special armoured batteries) to bombard Kronstadt and St Petersburg! (Black 2005, p. 126; Lambert, 2011). By the terms of the Treaty of Paris of March 1856, Russia was required to accept the neutralization of the Black Sea with no Russian (or Turkish) warships to be permitted to use these waters (Turkish forces would be redeployed to the Aegean) and all Russian fortifications on the Crimean coast to be demolished. The question was, who would enforce these provisions and for how long? Fourteen years later, when international attention was focused on the humiliation of France by Prussian forces in the 1870 Franco-Prussian War, Russia's brilliant Foreign Minister, Prince. Gorchakov, seized the opportunity to repudiate the Black Sea clauses of the 1856 Treaty of Paris and re-establish Russia's Black Sea Fleet at Sevastopol. The Russian Black Sea Fleet continues to operate from Sevastopol (Schwartz, 2014).

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